

STAKEHOLDER-ORIENTED *PHILAEENUS SPUMARIUS* SAMPLING PROCEDURES

R. ROBERTO¹, V. RUSSO², C. DONGIOVANNI⁶, V. CAVALIERI⁵, M. SAPONARI⁵, G. GILIOLI⁴, D. BOSCO³ F. PORCELLI^{1*}

¹ DISSPA UNIBA ALDO MORO, VIA AMENDOLA 165/A – 70126 BARI; ² CIHEAM-IAM BARI, VIA CEGLIE 9, 70010 VALENZANO (BA) ITALY. ³ DISAFA UNITO, GRUGLIASCO, TO, ITALY. ⁴ DMMT UNIBS, BRESCIA, ITALY. ⁵ CNR ISTITUTO PER LA PROTEZIONE SOSTENIBILE DELLE PIANTE UOS BARI (IPSP), SS BARI, 70126 BARI, ITALY. ⁶ CENTRO DI RICERCA, SPERIMENTAZIONE E FORMAZIONE IN AGRICOLTURA “BASILE CARAMIA”, LOCOROTONDO, BARI, ITALY.

***Corresponding author: francesco.porcelli@uniba.it**

The sampling of *Philaenus spumarius* (L.) (Ps), as developed in the EFSA Procurement [Collection of data and information on biology and control of vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* (RC/EFSA/ALPHA/2015/01)] is based on an intensive sampling design aiming at providing detailed information on the phenology and the local population dynamics of the pest. Monitoring for control purposes requires the survey of wide areas to the purpose of forecasting the biological events that elicit the control actions. In accordance with the objectives of POnTE WP5 we have been elaborating sampling procedures and tools to gather data useful for the design of control methods and candidate vector surveys. *Philaenus spumarius* lifecycle is peculiar as it is hemimetabolous with juveniles living in a froth and free-living adults. This biological peculiarity strongly suggests to use two different sampling protocols, one tailored for juveniles in spittle and another for the adults on herbaceous and woody hosts. The sampling unit should include a full herbaceous cover (for the spittle identification and counting) where spittle are counted in subsampling units framed by a transect. We collect Ps juvenile(s) by cutting the plant part with the spittle and dipping it in a single saline solution flask together with unit data. Nymphs in saline solution can be easily sieved out later, and transferred in ethanol with the accompanying dataset. To collect Ps adults from herbaceous or woody hosts, we use a normalized (38 cm Ø) sweeping net. We modified the net by replacing the conventional fabric sac with a net-like screen (1,5 x1,5 mm) one provided with a detachable single-sampling plastic collecting bag. After few swept (sampling subunit) on herbs or tree branches, we promptly add data into the plastic bag before detached and seal it. Bags are stored in fridges for days to kill the collected insect, then samples are stored in ethanol. Field trials with absolute beginner volunteers showed that, following 30 minutes of training, most of the volunteers are able to sample for juveniles and adults. Subsampling for juveniles takes about 10' by a two-person team that can also sample for adults ten subunits in the same time lapse. Finally, skilled operators shall identify the specimens.